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LEGAL ASPECTS OF WORKPLACE VIDEO SURVEILLANCE

Abstract: *The optimization of video surveillance in the workplace is a complex and multifaceted issue which is regulated by a variety of legislative acts and by-laws. This article explores the legal framework governing video surveillance in the workplace and the implications it manifests on the employment relationship in North Macedonia. The use of video surveillance in the workplace is subject to numerous legal requirements, including the need for Technical and Organizational Measures (TOMs) to ensure the security of the collected employees' personal data. The article also discusses the role of Data Protection Impact Assessments (DPIAs) in determining whether video surveillance in the workplace is necessary and justified. Overall, this article provides an in-depth analysis of the legal and regulatory landscape surrounding video surveillance in the workplace, and highlights the importance of considering the implications for both employers and employees in the context of employment relationships.*

Keywords: *employment relationship, workplace video surveillance, employee monitoring, data protection.*

1. Introduction

The issue of privacy has been the subject matter of ongoing debates from antiquity to the present day. Daniel Solove (2010) underlines that "people in nearly all societies have debated issues of privacy, ranging from gossip to eavesdropping to surveillance" (Solove, 2010: 4). Privacy preservation in

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multiple shapes and forms has been an important issue both for the public and for individuals. The rise of technology in the second half of the 20th century and the first quarter of the 21st century, mainly in the USA as one of the leading countries in advanced technology in this period, has generated the initial challenge of properly addressing the ethical considerations on the limitations on employee surveillance, in the context of employment (Ajunwa, Crawford, Schultz, 2017: 740-745). From today's perspective, considering the notion of surveillance, Kirstie Ball (2021) specifies:

“An act of surveillance always involves the purposeful gathering of information about something or someone. That information is then rationally and systemically analysed and the outcome of that analysis is then used to influence the behaviour of the original surveillance target. For a phenomenon to qualify as surveillant, two elements need to be present: data must be gathered and analysed, and then applied in a process of influence over the original data target. Surveillance always involves an exercise of power.” (Ball, 2021: 10).

Based on the instruments applied in the course of surveillance, some authors classify surveillance systems into electronic and non-electronic ones. Electronic surveillance systems generally include computer surveillance, telephone tapping, video surveillance, workplace surveillance, and mobile phone surveillance (Rajpoot, Jensen, 2015: 69-92).

Nowadays, video surveillance is commonly used both in public place and at the workplace (Senior, 2009: 35-36). In the context of employment, some authors underline that surveillance provides employers with absolute and relative data about the employees' conduct in the workplace, for the purposes of determining: whether employees are fulfilling their contractual obligations; how much reward they should receive based on their net contribution to the organization; and how their work can be coordinated in time and space (Sewell, 2012: 303).

The proliferation of video surveillance has sparked debates about the trade-off between security and privacy, underscoring the need for comprehensive data protection frameworks to balance these competing interests. In the context of employment, the employer is obliged to respect the privacy of all employees, which includes the operations and activities of video surveillance on the work premises and work equipment, regardless of whether the employee works from the provided and determined work premises by the employer or whether the work is conducted remotely or from home (Bailey, 2022: 527-551).

In that context, the EU General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679 (GDPR) is currently the toughest privacy and security law in the world that addresses

data processing, data storing, and data collecting practices by Data Controllers and Data Processors. Under the EU GDPR, the employers mainly act as Controllers, while the employees as Data Subjects. Some argue that the GDPR has also an “extraterritorial” application (Ryngaert, Taylor, 2020: 5-9). In line with the GDPR principles of accountability and transparency, the employers should enable the exercise of respective employees’ rights in a transparent and responsible manner; thus, employers should appropriately communicate their monitoring or data collecting practices to the employees and provide opportunities to the employees to exercise their related rights, either when working in a given workplace secured by the employer or when working remotely from home. As for workplace video surveillance, the employers should aspire to promptly address and mitigate the circumstances where that employees may feel a sense of distrust and discomfort when subjected to constant video surveillance in the workplace, which raises the issue of proportionality and purpose limitation on workplace video surveillance (Chory, Vela, Avtgis, 2015: 23-43). If workplace video surveillance increases the job stress, this factor can also have a negative impact on productivity (Rehman, 2023: 60-62). If the use of video surveillance in the workplace leads to increased stress and decreased productivity among employees, the employers have misused or miscalculated and miscommunicated the optimal environment of workplace video surveillance. As pointed out by Ball (2021), having in mind that video surveillance includes the effectiveness of policy and management communication, the following factors are important:

Transparency: the placement of cameras; what data are captured and why; technological capabilities and data storage; and policies on data sharing and purpose of use;

Access: who has access to technology and data; who can control the data collection process; the security of data storage and who can use the footage;

Equality: whether camera placement targets and collects data only about certain groups or individuals; whether data on all groups is processed and stored in the same manner; whether there are different outcomes for different groups (Ball, 2021: 27).

2. The Macedonian local context of workplace video surveillance

When it comes to the European data protection culture, James Whitman observes that “continental privacy protections are, at their core, a form of protection of a right to respect and personal dignity.” (Whitman, 2004: 1161). There are also views that, as technology advances, it is crucial for policymakers to implement robust data protection mechanisms to ensure that

individuals' privacy rights are upheld in the era of AI and video surveillance (Van Rijmenam, 2023).¹ Below we will outline the applicable laws and by-laws that regulate the workplace video surveillance in the Republic of North Macedonia.

2.1. Legislative acts that directly or implicitly regulate video surveillance in the context of the employment relationship

In the Republic of North Macedonia, the two main legislative acts that cover the protection of employees' personal data and regulate video surveillance in the context of employment are: the Labour Relations Act, and the Personal Data Protection Act.

Within the framework of Labour Relations Act² (hereinafter: the LRA), which includes the basic labour-related definitions, "employment relationship" is defined as a contractual relationship between the employee and the employer in which the employee voluntarily participates in the organized process of work for the employer, for salary and other income, personally performs the work continuously according to the instructions and under the supervision of the employer (Article 5 § 1 of the LRA). Under an extensive interpretation of the said legal provision, the notion of employer's supervision, which is regulated under many principled circumstances by the Personal Data Protection Act³ (hereinafter: the PDPA), can be interpreted as supervising the work of the employees, including the use of video surveillance in limited circumstances.

On the other hand, the Labour Relations Act imposes an obligation on the employer to protect the personality and the privacy of the employee. As the law states, the employer is obliged to protect and respect the personality and dignity of the employee, as well as to take care and protect the employee's privacy (Article 43 § 1 of the LRA). Notably, when it comes to video surveillance, whenever a video or image of an individual is captured by video surveillance

¹ Van Rijmenam, M. (2023). *Privacy in the Age of AI: Risks, Challenges and Solutions*, Retrieved 26 February 2024, from <https://www.thedigitalspeaker.com/privacy-age-ai-risks-challenges-solutions>.

² The Labour Relations Act, *Official Gazette of the Republic of Macedonia* No. 62/05, 106/08, 161/08, 114/09, 130/09, 50/10, 52/10, 124/10, 47/11, 11/12, 39/12, 13/13, 25/13, 170/13, 187/13, 113/14, 20/15, 33/15, 72/15, 129/15, 27/16, 120/18, and *Official Gazette of the Republic of North Macedonia* No. 110/19, 267/20 and 151/21.

³ The Personal Data Protection Act, *Official Gazette of the Republic of North Macedonia* no. 42/20 and 294/21. It should be noted that the Personal Data Protection Act has been almost entirely transposed as an expedient normative framework from the EU General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679 (GDPR).

and used to identify that person either directly or indirectly, it is considered personal data. In view of the above, the legislator introduced a separate article regulating the protection of employees' personal data within the framework of the labour relations law. Thus, personal data of employees can be collected, processed, used and delivered to third parties only if it is envisaged by this or another law, or if it is necessary for the exercise of rights and obligations from the employment relationship or in connection with the employment relationship (Article 44 § 1 of the LRA). Personal data of employees can be collected, processed, used and delivered to third parties only by the employer or the employee who has been specifically authorized by the employer for this purpose (Article 44 § 2 of the LRA). Accordingly, in case there is no longer a legal ground for the collection of employees' personal data, the collected personal data must be immediately deleted and cease to be used (Article 44 § 3 of the LRA).

Regarding the issues related to video surveillance, the Personal Data Protection Act specifies the following aspects that must be adhered to by the Data Controller, i.e. the employer:

- Inapplicability of personal data processing through video surveillance by physical persons exclusively for the purpose of monitoring activities in one's home;
- Obligation to issue a Notice on video surveillance, which contains:
 - information that video surveillance is being carried out;
 - the name/title of the Data Controller who performs the video surveillance; and
 - information about the way in which information can be obtained about where and how long the recordings from the video surveillance system are kept.
- Video surveillance can only be carried out in the area that is sufficient to fulfill the goals for which it was set;
- Obligation to notify the employees about performing video surveillance in official or business premises;
- Obligation to retain and preserve the recordings made during video surveillance, which are kept until the objectives for which it is performed are fulfilled, but not longer than 30 days, except in other types of specific cases (Article 89 of the PDPA).

When it comes to personal data processing through a video surveillance monitoring system, the legislator also provided a possibility of performing

video surveillance of the employer's (official or business) work premises. Thus, the Personal Data Protection Act specifies:

- The employer as a Controller can carry out video surveillance in official or business premises if it is necessary for the following purposes:
 - Protection of human life or health;
 - Protection of property;
- Protecting the life and health of employees due to the nature of the work;
- Providing control over entry and exit from official premises or business premises for security purposes only;
- The employer as a Controller should arrange the way of performing video surveillance by enacting a special (internal) act prescribed by the Personal Data Protection Agency;
- The employer acting as a Controller is prohibited from performing video surveillance in wardrobes, changing rooms, sanitary units and other similar rooms (Art. 89 of the PDPA).

The general rule regarding video surveillance is that recordings taken during video surveillance are kept until the objectives for which it is carried out are fulfilled, but not longer than 30 days, unless a longer period is provided by another law (Article 89 of the PDPA).

The legislator further obliges the employer acting in the capacity of a Controller to periodically evaluate the results achieved by the video surveillance system, in a manner and form prescribed by the Personal Data Protection Agency. The stated periodic assessment of the achieved results is planned to be carried out every two years, and especially in view of:

- the further need to use the video surveillance system;
- the purpose or purposes for performing video surveillance; and
- possible technical solutions for replacing the video surveillance system (Article 92 § 3 of the PDPA).

Finally, the legislator also provided misdemeanor fines when the video surveillance is inappropriately performed by the employer acting in the capacity of a Controller, as follows:

- A fine in the amount of 1,000 to 10,000 EUR (in Macedonian denars equivalent) will be imposed against a legal entity-Controller, in this case an employer, if:

- it performs video surveillance contrary to the provisions of Article 89 of the Personal Data Protection Act, which refers to video surveillance;
- it processes personal data through a video surveillance system contrary to the provisions of Article 90 of the Personal Data Protection Act, which refers to the processing of personal data through a video surveillance system; and if
- it does not perform analysis and periodic evaluation according to the provisions of Article 92 of the Personal Data Protection Act, which refers to the analysis and periodic assessment of the results achieved by the video surveillance system (Article 112 § 1, items 1,2 and 4 of the PDPA).

In view of the aforesaid article, the law also indicates that a fine in the amount of 100 to 500 EUR (in Macedonian denar equivalent) will be imposed on the responsible person in the legal entity-Controller for an offense related to the video surveillance (Article 112 § 3 of the PDPA), while a fine in the amount of 100 to 250 EUR (in Macedonian denar equivalent) will be imposed on a natural person-Controller or processor for an offense related to video surveillance (Article 112 § 4 of the PDPA).

2.2. By-laws that regulate video surveillance in the Republic of North Macedonia and have an implicative impact in the context of employment relations.

Bearing in mind that some employers acting in the capacity of Controllers decide to resort to installing a video monitoring system and equipment on work premises, the by-laws that regulate video surveillance and have an implicative impact in employment contexts are:

- Rulebook on the content and form of the act for performance of video surveillance, *Official Gazette of the Republic of North Macedonia*, No. 122/2020;
- Rulebook on amending the Rulebook on the content and form of the act for performance of video surveillance, *Official Gazette of North Macedonia*, No. 280/2021;
- Rulebook on the content of the analysis of video surveillance purpose/ purposes and the report from the periodic review of the results achieved by the video surveillance system, *Official Gazette of North Macedonia*, No. 122/2020.

For the purpose of restating and summarizing the obligations that the employers need to abide by, there is the compliance cycle which needs to be respected by the employer in case of integrating workplace video surveillance; the set of steps includes:

- Analysis of the purpose for which video surveillance is installed in the workplace;
- Defining the purpose for which video surveillance is installed in the workplace, e.g.:
 - Protection of life and health of people;
 - Property protection (employer's belongings);
 - Protection of life and health of employees due to the nature of the job;
 - Control entry to and exit from official/business premises only for security purposes;
- Conducting video surveillance at the workplace within the principle of proportionality and prohibiting video surveillance in wardrobes, changing rooms, sanitary facilities, toilets and similar rooms;
- Notification on video surveillance in the workplace, which has to be: clearly written, placed in a visible location, and posted in a place that will enable employees to be notified that video surveillance is being carried out;
- Periodic assessment of the results obtained by the video surveillance system, which has to be revised and re-evaluated at least once every two years;
- Recording storage period which applies until the moment of fulfillment of the objectives for which the video surveillance is carried out, but not longer than 30 days;
 - Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) for workplace video surveillance but only when applicable; it is mainly applied if the employer processes personal data by using systematic observation and monitoring of publicly accessible space on a large scale.

3. Requirements of Technical and Organizational Measures (TOMs) for secure video surveillance in the workplace

Plenty of debates and roundtables have been organized within the data protection community on various platforms. It has been stated on many

occasions that video surveillance systems have the potential to capture vast amounts of personal data, making it imperative for organizations to prioritize data protection measures to prevent unauthorized access and misuse of such data.⁴ In the context of employment, some voices echo the argument that the proliferation of workplace surveillance technologies poses significant threats to employees' privacy and autonomy, whereupon employees must act as gatekeepers against data misuse (Hu, 2021: 115-151) and employers must balance their legitimate interests in monitoring productivity with the employees' rights to privacy and data protection (ICO, 2023a: 7).⁵

Generally, the implementation and operationalization of the Technical and Organizational Measures (TOMs) falls on the Processor of the personal data, i.e. the responsible party that processes the workplace video surveillance data on behalf of the Controller. Most commonly, as underlined by the Information Commissioner's Office (ICO), the UK's Data Protection Authority, one party (i.e. one employer) cannot be both a Controller and a Processor for the same processing activity, except in particular cases where the personal data is being processed for different purposes (ICO, 2023b).⁶ Notably, some Data Protection Authorities, such as the Swiss Federal Data Protection and Information Commissioner (FDPIC), outline the importance of developing and implementing Technical and Organizational Measures as a combination that can also be used in the context of workplace video surveillance, for preventing the destruction and loss of data, as well as errors, falsification, unauthorized access, etc. (FDPIC, 2024).⁷ Additionally, the implementation of effective Technical and Organizational Measures is critical for preventing misuse and abuse of video surveillance systems in the workplace; moreover, adequate

⁴Some authors have provided a Data Misuse Classification, a classification that comprises eleven categories of personal data misuse. For a detailed overview, see: Kröger, J.L., Miceli, M., Müller, F. (2021). How Data Can Be Used Against People: A Classification of Personal Data Misuses. *SSRN Electronic Journal*, 3–4.

⁵The Information Commissioner's Office (ICO), which is the UK's Data Protection Authority, prepared and published a guideline on lawful monitoring in the workplace. See: ICO (2023a). *Employment Practices and Data protection: Monitoring Workers*, 4 Oct. 2023, Retrieved 23 Feb. 2024 from <https://ico.org.uk/media/for-organisations/uk-gdpr-guidance-and-resources/employment-information/employment-practices-and-data-protection-monitoring-workers-1-0.pdf>.

⁶ICO (2023b). *How do you determine whether you are a controller or processor?*. Retrieved 23 Feb. 2024 from <https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/uk-gdpr-guidance-and-resources/controllers-and-processors/controllers-and-processors/how-do-you-determine-whether-you-are-a-controller-or-processor>.

⁷Federal Data Protection and Information Commissioner (2024). *Guide to Technical and Organisational Data Protection Measures (TOM)*, 15 January 2024; Retrieved 28 Feb. 2024 from https://www.edoeb.admin.ch/dam/edoeb/en/Dokumente/datenschutz/leitfaden_tom.pdf

organizational measures in combination with Privacy Impact Assessments (PIAs) are essential for ensuring that video surveillance in the workplace is properly conducted to preserve individual rights and freedoms.

In that context the European Data Protection Board (EDPB) has published the Guidelines on processing personal data through video devices (2020).⁸ Within the Guidelines, the EDPB underlines that the Controller must adequately protect all components of a video surveillance system and data under all stages, i.e. during storage (data at rest), transmission (data in transit), and processing (data at use) (EDPB, 2020: 30-31). Regarding organizational measures, apart from potentially conducting a Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA), the European Data Protection Board suggests considering the following issues in the process of creating video surveillance policies and procedures:

- Who is responsible for management and operation of the video surveillance system;
- Purpose and scope of the video surveillance project;
- Appropriate and prohibited use (where and when video surveillance is allowed and not allowed (e.g. use of hidden cameras and audio in addition to video recording));
- Transparency measures referred as Transparency and information obligations;⁹
- How video is recorded and for what duration, including archival storage of video recordings related to security incidents;
- Who must undergo relevant training and when;
- Who has access to video recordings and for what purposes;
- Operational procedures (e.g. by whom and from where video surveillance is monitored, what to do in case of a data breach incident);

⁸ European Data Protection Board (2020). *Guidelines 3/2019 on processing of personal data through video devices, v2.0.*, 29 January 2020, Retrieved 26 February 2024 from https://edpb.europa.eu/sites/default/files/files/file1/edpb_guidelines_201903_video_devices_en.pdf

⁹ As underlined by the European Data Protection Board, transparency and information obligations divide the required information that should be provided by the employer that acts as a Controller. The first layer of information is setting up the warning sign that the given premises (including in the workplace) is under surveillance. The second layer of information relates to the obligation to make the monitoring information available at a place easily accessible to the data subject (e.g. a complete information sheet available at a central location or displayed on an easy accessible poster).

- What procedures external parties need to follow in order to request video recordings, and procedures for denying or granting such requests;
- Procedures for VSS procurement, installation and maintenance;
- Incident management and recovery procedures (EDPB, 2020: 31).

When it comes to technical measures, the EDPB Guidelines outline the measures that should be undertaken to protect the video surveillance (VSS) system:

- Physical security: to protect the VSS equipment from theft, vandalism, natural disasters, man-made catastrophes and accidental damage (electrical surges, extreme temperatures, spilled coffee);
- System and data security protection against intentional and unintentional interference with the system, including:
 - Protection of the entire VSS infrastructure (including remote cameras, cabling and power supply) against physical tampering and theft;
 - Protection of footage transmission with communication channels secure against interception;
 - Data encryption;
 - Use of hardware and software based solutions such as firewalls, antivirus or intrusion detection systems against cyber-attacks;
 - Detection of failures of components, software and interconnections;
 - Means to restore availability and access to the system in the event of a physical or technical incident;
- Access control: to ensure that only authorized people can access the system and data, while at the same time others are prevented from doing it, by:
 - Ensuring that all premises where monitoring by video surveillance is done and where video footage is stored are secured against unsupervised access by third parties;
 - Positioning monitors (especially in open areas, like a reception) in such a way that only authorized operators can view them;
 - Defining and enforcing procedures for granting, changing and revoking physical and logical access;
 - Implementing methods and means of user authentication and

authorization, including e.g. passwords length and change frequency;

- Recording and regularly reviewing user-taken actions (to the system and data);
- Continuously monitoring and detecting access failures, and addressing the identified weaknesses as soon as possible (EDPB, 2020: 32).

Both from the perspectives of the European Data Protection Board and the data protection community in Europe, the relevant Technical and Organizational Measures (TOMs) that should be taken into consideration when introducing workplace video surveillance lead to a conclusion that the following checklist should be observed and to some degree required for workplace surveillance by employers, where the employees' privacy may be affected. In a nutshell, the checklist includes:

- Information security related matters:
 - Implementing physical and logical access control measures on preventing unauthorized personnel accessing the video footage
 - Maintaining password-protected and locked room where the surveillance cameras and the recording are stored (user control)
 - Designing encrypted data storage environment for ensuring the data is safely stored from an information security perspective (storage control)
 - Utilizing high-quality and tamper-proof cameras for ensuring optimal video data accuracy (data integrity)
- Data protection related matters:
 - Conducting periodic audit assessments as prescribed by the supervising Data Protection Authority
 - Creating and publishing Workplace Video Surveillance Policies or Employee Privacy Policies where processing of personal data from a video surveillance system is being transparently acknowledged
 - Setting the video surveillance process in the workplace in accordance to the purpose limitation principle and ensuring that it is not overextended by infringing the the privacy of the employees
- Combined matters:
 - Assigning a specific internal employee or an external person as

a process owner, or even a responsible team for managing and monitoring the video surveillance system

- Conducting information security and data protection staff training sessions for the internal or external video surveillance operators.

4. Conducting Data Protection Impact Assessment on the workplace video surveillance systems: Should it be a required activity to be undertaken by default?

The UK Data Protection Authority, the Information Commissioner's Office (ICO), notes that, if the use of CCTV is likely to result in a high risk to people, the Controller will also need to carry out a Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) for the purpose of identifying the impact that the use of CCTV may have on people and reducing any risks (ICO, 2023c).¹⁰ The Data Protection Impact Assessment is also addressed in the General Data Protection Regulation,¹¹ which states: "Where a type of processing in particular using new technologies, and taking into account the nature, scope, context and purposes of the processing, is likely to result in a high risk to the rights and freedoms of natural persons, the Controller shall, prior to the processing, carry out an assessment of the impact of the envisaged processing operations on the protection of personal data" (Article 35 § 1 of the GDPR). In addition, as noted in Article 35 § 3 of the GDPR, a Data Protection Impact Assessment can be required in the event of:

1. conducting a systematic and extensive evaluation of personal aspects relating to natural persons, which is based on automated processing (including profiling), and on which decisions are based that produce legal effects concerning the natural person or significantly affect the natural person in a similar manner;
2. processing special categories of data on a large scale;
3. a systematic monitoring of a publicly accessible area on a large scale.

By comparison, there are views which streamline that the California Consumer Privacy Act (CCPA), which is considered to be the landmark law

¹⁰ICO (2023 c). *Installing CCTV? Things you need to do first* (updated 23 June 2023); <https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/advice-for-small-organisations/whats-new/blogs/installing-cctv-things-you-need-to-do-first>.

¹¹Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation); <https://gdpr-info.eu/>

in the USA that secures new privacy rights for California consumers, may require Data Protection Impact Assessments (DPIAs) from companies whose processing of employees' personal data (including profiling employees) poses a substantial risk to privacy, namely, as noted by some authors, the "DPIAs are tools to prompt organizations to engage in sufficient planning and self-reflection to foresee potential risks and to integrate mitigations into their design and planning processes by considering both the data types and the processing activities that pose high risks to individuals" (King, Meinhardt, 2024: 27).

Some scholars also observe that employers must prioritize the implementation of DPIAs, such as in the context of deployment of workplace video surveillance systems, to safeguard against privacy infringements by (highly) risky processing operations (Demetzou, 2019: 4-6). Ultimately, as noted by other authors, how a DPIA is conducted in practice and what it represents depends on the contextual basis of conducting a DPIA on a workplace video surveillance system within a given organization; the end goal should serve as "a good instrument to support decision-makers and developers, if it is not merely regarded as a compulsory exercise but as a useful tool" (Friedewald, Schiering, Martin, Hallinan, 2022: 439).

5. Conclusion

Some authors believe that the employees generally tend to desire more freedom and less monitoring (Yerby, 2013: 47). Other authors underline that "employers monitoring and attempting to control their employees' work, as well as their private lives is nothing new" (Chory, Vela, Avtgis, 2015: 24-25). With that in mind, setting up the aim, scope and context of video surveillance in the workplace, and assessing whether such monitoring is required at the workplace, depends on the legal justification and the rationale of using video surveillance for these purposes. Several decades ago, some authors pointed out that video surveillance may be used for specific purposes, enabling employers to prevent theft, fraudulent activities, and other workplace-related violations (Vaught, Taylor, Vaught, 2000: 107-114). D'Urso pointed out that "the issues surrounding employee monitoring have garnered renewed attention because of concerns over employee privacy rights" (D'Urso, 2006: 285). In this regard, Moussa observes that "new technologies have not only offered organizations reasons to monitor employees' behavior, but these technologies have also provided new methods and techniques to perform employee monitoring. Thus, technology must be treated with caution and discretion" (Moussa, 2015: 10). Even though video surveillance at work is becoming increasingly common in many workplaces, Martin and Freeman (2003) observe that "it

raises concerns in all areas of society – business organizations, employee interest groups, privacy advocates, civil libertarians, lawyers, professional ethicists, and every combination possible. Each advocate has its own rationale for or against employee monitoring whether it be economic, legal, or ethical.” (Martin, Freeman, 2003: 353).

As employers seek to enhance security, monitor the employee efficiency, and prevent theft or other illegal activities, there several factors that employers should take into account when they consider engaging in workplace video surveillance practices or decide to periodically reassess the existing workplace video surveillance practice. Here are the key takeaways:

- Video surveillance in the workplace is not always necessary;
- In case it is necessary, workplace video surveillance needs to be justified and conducted lawfully, in line with Article 6 of the EU GDPR and the corresponding articles of the transposed Personal Data Protection Acts of North Macedonia;
- Employees’ privacy should not be violated while they are at work; workplace video surveillance should not target the employees, analyze their conduct, monitor their private correspondence on private mobile devices, or serve as a profiling tool;
- Video surveillance in the workplace should not be intrusive and should not cause the employees’ stress, negative emotions or reduced productivity;
- Respecting the employees’ data protection rights is important for properly navigating and streamlining how the established set of data protection rights envisaged in the EU GDPR and local data protection laws can be exercised in the context of workplace video surveillance;
- Even in cases when it is not mandatory by a legal requirement, an employer may go a step further by adding an extra layer to the data protection compliance, by appointing an independent Data Protection Officer who can properly take care of lawful and proportionate video surveillance in the workplace. This extra step is an added value for the employer that acts as a Data Controller towards the employees.

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Правилник за содржината на анализата на целта, односно целите за која се поставува видеонадзорот и извештајот од извршена периодична оценка на постигнатите резултати од системот за вршење видеонадзор (Rulebook on the content of the analysis of video surveillance purpose/purposes and the report from the periodic review of the results achieved by the video surveillance system), *Службен весник на Република Северна Македонија* бр. 122/2020, <https://www.slvesnik.com.mk/Issues/d7f82d49d880401290d92beaf6dff1a.pdf>

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ПРАВНИ АСПЕКТИ ВИДЕО НАДЗОРА НА РАДНОМ МЕСТУ

Резиме

Оптимизација видео надзора на радном месту је сложено и вишеструко питање које је у националном контексту регулисано разним законским и подзаконским актима. Овај чланак истражује правни оквир видео надзора на радном месту и импликације које он има на радни однос у Северној Македонији. Коришћење видео надзора на радном месту подлеже бројним законским условима, укључујући и техничке и организационе мере којима би се осигурала безбедност прикупљених личних података радника. Поред тога, у чланку се говори о улози процене утицаја на заштиту података у одређивању да ли је видео надзор на радном месту неопходан и оправдан. Све у свему, овај чланак пружа детаљну анализу правног и регулаторног окружења које се односи на видео надзор на радном месту и наглашава важност разматрања импликација како за послодавце тако и за запослене у контексту радног односа.

Кључне речи: радни однос, видео надзор радног места, надзор запослених, заштита података.

